

Aroma-Active Compounds Contributing to Aged Riesling Character

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Abstract

The Riesling varietal, which originates from the Rhine region of Germany, is globally one of the most popular white wine grapes. Young Riesling wines are favoured for their fruity and floral character; however, lesser-known aged Rieslings possess a more complex aroma profile with notes of sherry, maple, and a balanced petrol character. Several fruity esters and alcohols are known to contribute to the tropical fruit and floral character of young Rieslings, but the odorants that contribute to the complexity of aged Rieslings are not well characterised. Thus, the goal of this study was to employ aroma extract dilution analysis (AEDA) and stable isotope dilution assays (SIDA) to identify and quantitate the key odorants that contribute to the aroma of a ten-year-old Joh. Jos. Prüm Riesling. This study afforded 34 odorants with flavour dilution (FD) factors greater than 1, with 2-phenylethanol (floral, rose) and ethyl butanoate (fruity) having the highest FD factor of 1024. Upon quantitation by SIDA, the odorant with the highest odour activity value (OAV) was wine lactone (coconut, OAV 460) followed by ethyl octanoate (fruity, OAV 240) and ethyl hexanoate (fruity, OAV 97). Other odorants with OAVs greater than 1, which may contribute to the complex aroma of the aged Riesling, included 5-ethyl-3-hydroxy-4-methyl-(5H)-furan-2-one (sherry, OAV 33), 1,1,6-trimethyl-1,2-dihydronaphthalene (petrol, OAV 6.4), and 3-methylbutan-1-ol (malty, OAV 3.6). This study has provided a comprehensive evaluation of key odorants contributing to the characteristic aroma of a bottle-aged Riesling and provides a foundation for future studies to probe the influence of each odorant in the overall aroma of aged Riesling.

Keywords: aged Riesling, aroma extract dilution analysis, stable isotope dilution assays

Introduction

The Riesling varietal originates from a region of south-western Germany surrounding the Rhine River and is the most commonly grown variety in Germany. The varietal has gained global popularity for its refreshing fruity and floral character and is now grown in cool climates throughout the world. The aroma of young Riesling is described as having a predominant fruity and floral character with notes of citrus, tropical fruit and even honey. Previous studies have shown that several esters and alcohols are responsible for the aroma of young Riesling [1, 2]. However, the odorants that contribute to the more complex aroma profile of bottle-aged Riesling, which include notes of sherry, maple, and petrol, are not fully understood.

Experimental

To characterise the aroma of a bottle aged Riesling the wine was extracted with organic solvent and distilled by solvent assisted flavour evaporation (SAFE) to isolate the volatile compounds. Aroma extract dilution analysis (AEDA) of the SAFE isolate was employed to identify which volatile compounds were aroma-active and stable isotope dilution assays (SIDA) were used to quantitate aroma-active compounds.

Selected Wine

The bottle aged Riesling selected for this study was a 2009 Riesling Kabinett produced by Joh. Jos. Prüm. The wine was purchased from a local distributor and maintained at 2 °C prior to analysis.

Extraction and Isolation of volatile compounds by solvent assisted flavour evaporation (SAFE)

Volatile compounds were extracted from the wine with distilled diethyl ether (Honeywell Burdick and Jackson, Muskegon, MI) and distilled by SAFE. Wine (50 mL), NaCl (5 g), and diethyl ether (100 mL) were combined and extracted by manual shaking (5 min). The aqueous phase was re-extracted with additional diethyl ether (50 mL) and the organic phases combined. The organic extract was then washed with saturated NaCl solution two times (2 x 50 mL) and then dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The volatile compounds were distilled from the organic extract by SAFE with the apparatus maintained at 41 °C and under vacuum (10⁻³ mbar). The SAFE isolate was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and condensed to 200 µL with a Vigreux column followed by a gentle stream of N₂.

Aroma Extract Dilution Analysis (AEDA)

The SAFE isolate was serially diluted with diethyl ether to generate eleven samples decreasing in concentration and designated as flavour dilution 1 (FD 1) to flavour dilution 1024 (FD 1024). Each sample was individually

analysed by gas chromatography-olfactometry (GC-O) beginning with FD 1 (the undiluted SAFE isolate) and ending with FD 1024. Each aroma detected by GC-O was assigned an odour quality and the highest flavour dilution that each aroma could be perceived was determined. The identity of each odorant was determined through a combination of odour quality, retention index, and mass spectrum.

GC-O was carried out on an Agilent 7820A GC system with a flame ionization detector (FID) (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) fitted with a Zebtron ZB-FFAP GC column (30 m length, 0.32 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film thickness) from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA). A 1 µL sample was injected on column and carried by helium gas (1.5 mL/min) and separated with the following temperature program: initial temperature of 35 °C was held for 1 minute, ramp to 60 °C at 60 °C/min, ramp to 240 °C at 6 °C/min, and a final hold time of 10 minutes at 240 °C. At the end of the chromatographic column the effluent was split with a Y-splitter and half the effluent was channelled to a heated nose cone (250 °C) and the other half was channelled to the FID detector (250 °C, 40 mL/min hydrogen gas, 450 mL/min air, and 45 mL/min makeup gas).

Stable Isotope Dilution Assays (SIDA)

To quantitate each analyte, an isotopically labelled analogue was used as an internal standard. The isotopically labelled standards were acquired from commercial suppliers or synthesized in house, and a response factor for each analyte/standard pair was determined by GC-MS (Table 1). The isotopically labelled standards were volumetrically added to the wine prior to being extracted with diethyl ether, subjected to SAFE, and condensed according to the method described above. The resulting SAFE isolate was analysed by GC-MS and the odorants were quantitated using the previously determined response factors.

GC-MS was carried out on an Agilent 7820A GC system coupled to an Agilent 5977B mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA). A Zebtron ZB-FFAP GC capillary column (30 m length, 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film thickness) from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA) was used for chromatographic separation. A 1 µL sample was injected on column (35 °C) and carried by helium gas (1.5 mL/min). The following temperature program was used to achieve chromatographic separation: initial temperature of 35 °C was held for 1 minute, ramp to 60 °C at 60 °C/min, ramp to 250 °C at 6 °C/min, and a final hold time of 5 minutes at 250 °C. The MS detector was operated in electron impact ionization mode (70 eV), the MS source was held at 230 °C, and the MS quadrupole at 150 °C.

Table 1: Ions and response factors of odorants and labelled isotopes used for stable isotope dilution assays.

no.	odorant	labelled standard	ion (<i>m/z</i>)		
			analyte	standard	RF
1	ethyl isobutyrate ^a	ethyl isobutyrate-d2 ^d	116	118	0.98
2	ethyl butanoate ^a	ethyl butanoate-d3 ^e	116	119	0.96
3	(<i>S</i>)-ethyl 2-methylbutanoate ^a	(<i>S</i>)-ethyl 2-methylbutanoate-d9 ^e	102	107	0.86
4	ethyl 3-methylbutanoate ^a	ethyl 3-methylbutanoate-d2 ^d	85	87	0.58
5	2-methylpropan-1-ol ^a	2-methylpropan-1-ol-d7 ^f	74	81	1.66
7	2- and 3-methylbutan-1-ol ^a	3-methylbutan-1-ol-d4 ^e	70	74	1.22
8	ethyl hexanoate ^a	ethyl hexanoate-d11 ^e	99	110	0.83
11	cis-rose oxide ^a	cis-rose oxide-d2 ^f	139	141	0.62
13	ethyl octanoate ^a	ethyl octanoate-d15 ^e	127	142	0.80
14	acetic acid ^a	acetic acid- ¹³ C ₁ ^a	60	61	1.13
15	3-(methylsulphanyl)propanal ^a	3-(methylsulfonyl)propanal-d3 ^d	104	107	1.21
16	linalool ^a	linalool-d3 ^e	93	96	0.85
17	2-methylpropanoic acid ^a	2-methylpropanoic acid-d7 ^e	88	95	1.14
18	butanoic acid ^a	butanoic acid-d7 ^e	73	77	0.89
19a	2-methylbutanoic acid ^a	2-methylbutanoic acid-d9 ^e	57	66	1.05
19b	3-methylbutanoic acid ^a	3-methylbutanoic acid-d9 ^e	60	63	1.02
21	1,1,6-trimethyl-1,2-dihydronaphthalene ^b	1,1,6-trimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-d4 ^f	157	162	0.73
22	(<i>E</i>)-β-damascenone ^a	(<i>E</i>)-β-damascenone-d4 ^d	69	73	0.92
23	2-phenylethyl acetate ^a	2-phenylethyl acetate-d5 ^f	104	109	1.25
27	2-phenylethanol ^a	2-phenylethanol-d5 ^e	122	127	0.99
29	HDMF ^a	HDMF- ¹³ C ₂ ^a	128	130	0.96
31	wine lactone ^c	wine lactone-d3 ^d	166	169	0.94
32	5-ethyl-3-hydroxy-4-methyl-(5 <i>H</i>)-furan-2-one ^a	3-hydroxy-4,5-dimethylfuran-2(5 <i>H</i>)-one - ¹³ C ₂ ^d	142	130	1.29
33	2-phenylacetic acid ^a	2-phenylacetic acid-d5 ^g	91	96	0.90
34	4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde ^a	4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde-d3 ^e	152	155	0.21

^a reference standard purchased from Millipore Sigma (St. Louis, MO). ^b reference standard purchased from MuseChem (Fairfield, NJ). ^c reference standard purchased from eNovation Chemicals LLC (Green Brook, NJ). ^d labelled standard purchased from aromaLAB (Planegg, Germany). ^e labelled standard purchased from C/D/N Isotopes Inc. (Pointe-Clair, Quebec, Canada). ^f labelled standard synthesized in house. ^g labelled standard purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc. (Tewksbury, MA).

Results and discussion

To gain insight into the odorants that may be indicative of aged Riesling character, an individual wine that embodied these aged qualities was selected for a full aroma characterisation. The selected wine was a 2009 Riesling Kabinett produced by Joh. Jos. Prüm, a winery highly regarded for producing some of the highest quality Rieslings in Germany. The aroma of this wine is described as having prominent fruity, floral and citrus character with balanced acidity and more subtle notes of vanilla, coconut, caramel, sherry, maple, and petrol.

AEDA was employed to determine the odorants that were present in the aged Riesling, which could be perceived by GC-O, and the relative impact of each odorant. As a result, 34 odorants were identified with FD factors ≥ 1 (Figure 1). Ethyl butanoate and 2-phenylethanol, which exhibit fruity and rose odour characteristics respectively, had the highest FD factor (FD 1024). Other odorants with fruity and floral odour characteristics were identified with an FD factor of 256, namely (*S*)-ethyl 2-methylbutanoate, ethyl 3-methylbutanoate, ethyl hexanoate, ethyl octanoate, and (*E*)- β -damascenone. However, 2 and 3-methylbutan-1-ol (malty), HDMF (caramel), and 5-ethyl-3-hydroxy-4-methyl-(5*H*)-furan-2-one (sherry) also had FD factors of 256 and thus may be contributing to the complexity of aged Riesling aroma beyond the fruity and floral qualities.

Figure 1. Flavor dilution chromatogram of odorants identified in bottle aged Riesling wine by aroma extract dilution analysis. (1) ethyl isobutyrate; (2) ethyl butanoate; (3) (*S*)-ethyl 2-methylbutanoate; (4) ethyl 3-methylbutanoate; (5) 2-methylpropan-1-ol; (6) 3-methylbutyl acetate; (7) 2 and 3-methylbutan-1-ol; (8) ethyl hexanoate; (9) 1-octen-3-one; (10) hexanol; (11) cis-rose oxide; (12) (*Z*)-3-hexenol; (13) ethyl octanoate; (14) acetic acid; (15) 3-(methylsulphonyl)propanal; (16) linalool; (17) 2-methylpropanoic acid; (18) butanoic acid; (19) 2- and 3-methylbutanoic acid; (20) pentanoic acid; (21) 1,1,6-trimethyl-1,2-dihydronaphthalene; (22) (*E*)- β -damascenone; (23) 2-phenylethyl acetate; (24) hexanoic acid; (25) geraniol; (26) 2-methoxyphenol; (27) 2-phenylethanol; (28) γ -nonalactone; (29) HDMF; (30) sotolon; (31) wine lactone; (32) 5-ethyl-3-hydroxy-4-methyl-(5*H*)-furan-2-one; (33) 2-phenylacetic acid; (34) 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde.

To further probe the relative impact of each odorant in the matrix of the aged Riesling, odorants were accurately quantitated and odour activity values calculated. The odorants with high FD factors ($FD \geq 64$ and other selected odorants) were quantitated through the application of SIDAs, resulting in 14 quantitated odorants having OAVs ≥ 1 (Table 2). The odorants with the highest OAVs were wine lactone (coconut, OAV 460), ethyl octanoate (fruity, OAV 240), ethyl hexanoate (fruity, OAV 97), and (*E*)- β -damascenone (cooked apple, OAV 60). In addition to these and other fruity and floral odorants, some odorants that are not traditionally found in young Riesling wines also had OAVs ≥ 1 . 5-ethyl-3-hydroxy-4-methyl-(5*H*)-furan-2-one, which has not been previously identified in young Rieslings, was determined to have a relatively high OAV of 33. This compound imparts a sherry odour quality, which can be associated with aged Riesling. Likewise, 1,1,6-trimethyl-1,2-dihydronaphthalene (petrol) was determined to have an OAV of 6.4. The importance of this compound to the aroma of aged Riesling is supported by previous findings that this odorant is generated during bottle aging and imparts a petrol-like note to Riesling [3, 4]. Similarly, 3-methylbutan-1-ol (malty) was determined to have an OAV of 3.6. This compound has been previously identified as important to the aroma of sherry [5], another aged wine, and may also contribute to the malty notes associated with aged Riesling. This analysis has indicated several key odorants that exhibit odour qualities associated with aged Riesling character. Though these findings provide insight into odorants that may contribute to the unique aroma profile of aged Riesling, additional sensory experiments are needed to fully understand the complexity of aged Riesling aroma.

Table 2: Odorant concentrations, odour thresholds, and odour activity values of key odorants in bottle aged Riesling.

no.	odorant	odour quality	concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$) ^a	odour threshold ($\mu\text{g/L}$) ^b	OAV ^d
31	wine lactone	coconut	4.59	0.010	460
13	ethyl octanoate	fruity	481	2.0	240
8	ethyl hexanoate	fruity	483	5.0	97
22	(<i>E</i>)- β -damascenone	cooked apple	3.00	0.050	60
32	5-ethyl-3-hydroxy-4-methyl-(5 <i>H</i>)-furan-2-one	sherry	163	5.0	33
3	(<i>S</i>)-ethyl 2-methylbutanoate	fruity	21.6	1.0	22
15	3-(methylsulphanyl)propanal	cooked potato	8.55	0.43 ^c	20
1	ethyl isobutyrate	fruity	142	15	9.5
2	ethyl butanoate	fruity	141	20	7.1
21	1,1,6-trimethyl-1,2-dihydronaphthalene	petrol	12.9	2.0	6.4
11	cis-rose oxide	floral	1.18	0.20	5.9
7b	3-methylbutan-1-ol	malty	109000	30000	3.6
27	2-phenylethanol	rose	31000	10000	3.1
4	ethyl 3-methylbutanoate	fruity	6.85	3.0	2.3
5	2-methylpropan-1-ol	malty	32600	40000	<1
16	linalool	floral	9.99	15	<1
23	2-phenylethyl acetate	floral	139	250	<1
14	acetic acid	vinegar	94300	200000	<1
34	4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde	vanilla-like	89.5	200	<1
18	butanoic acid	sweaty	1390	10000	<1
19b	3-methylbutanoic acid	sweaty, rancid	239	3000	<1
19a	2-methylbutanoic acid	sweaty, rancid	174	3000	<1
7a	2-methylbutan-1-ol	malty	76.2	3700 ^c	<1
33	2-phenylacetic acid	honey	69.9	6100 ^c	<1
29	HDMF	caramel	2.62	500	<1
17	2-methylpropanoic acid	sweaty	857	200000	<1

^a mean of at least three data points. ^b odour thresholds determined in water/ ethanol (90/10, w/w) reported in [6]. ^c odour threshold determined in water reported in [7]. ^d odour activity value (concentration/odour threshold).

Conclusion

As a result of this study, 34 odorants with FD factors ≥ 1 were identified from an aged Riesling by AEDA and 26 of the odorants were quantitated by SIDAs. Several key odorants with OAVs ≥ 1 exhibited odour qualities such as coconut, sherry, petrol, and malty suggesting these odorants may be influential to the aroma of the bottle aged Riesling. Future studies, such as aroma recombination and omission experiments, are needed to further probe the impact of each odorant on the aroma of the aged Riesling.

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